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Unique Characteristics, Biometric Measurements, Management and Performance Parameters of Balochi Sheep

Author's Details:

¹Jehan, M., ²Bajwa, M. A., ^{2*}Tariq, M. M., ³Eyduran, E., ²Rafeeq, M., ²Mustafa, M. Z., ^{4,5}Ahmad, I., ⁵Patching, S. G., ⁶Waheed, A., ¹Ahmad, J., ²Khan, M. A., ¹Ahmad, F., ¹Fatih, A., ¹Ali, I., ¹Ahmed, M., ¹Amin, S.

⁽¹⁾Livestock and Dairy Development Department Balochistan, Quetta, Pakistan

⁽²⁾Center for Advanced Studies in Vaccinology and Biotechnology (CASVAB), University of Balochistan, Quetta, Pakistan ⁽³⁾Biometry and Genetics Unit, Department of Animal Science, Faculty of Agriculture, Iğdır University, Iğdır, Turkey ⁽⁴⁾Institute of Basic Medical Sciences, Khyber Medical University, Peshawar, Pakistan

⁽⁵⁾School of Biomedical Sciences and Astbury Centre for Structural Molecular Biology, University of Leeds, Leeds, UK

⁽⁶⁾Faculty of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Bahauddin Zakaria University, Multan, Pakistan

*Corresponding author's e-mail: tariqkianiraja@hotmail.com

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Abstract

This study was conducted to assess the characteristics, management practices, production systems and performance parameters of Balochi sheep in the Pakistan province of Balochistan. The Balochi breed is highly adapted to the harsh agro-climatic conditions of Balochistan. Data for Balochi sheep (n=7049) from fifteen different villages in three districts (Kalat, Mastung, Quetta) of Balochistan were collected regarding feeding, management practices, health practices and productive performance through proforma and individual perceptions. Body weights and other biometric measurements were recorded for rams and ewes from the three districts and from the Multi-Purpose Sheep Research Station Yetabad, Loralai (MSRSYL). The Balochi breed is a distinctive sheep with unique characteristics. They display a white body with a black, brown or spotted muzzle and legs. They have a firm medium-sized body, intermediate ears, Roman nose, pendulous belly, commonly polled and with a fat tail. Balochi sheep were found mostly in Kalat and in part of the Quetta division, and also thinly populated throughout the rest of the Balochistan province. Sexual dimorphism was evident for several traits, for example, it had a significant effect ($p < 0.05$) on body weight, body length, heart girth and wither height, whilst tail length did not vary significantly between the sexes ($p > 0.05$). Balochi sheep husbandry is favored in the region because of its adaptability, great survival rate and growth performance, however the returns from sheep production are marginal and low cost production is still a challenge.

Key words: Balochi sheep, biometric measurement, management, performance

INTRODUCTION

According to the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, Pakistan had a sheep (*Ovis aries*) population of 26.5 million in 2006 (<http://www.pbs.gov.pk/content/livestock-population>) of which there are at least 28 different breeds (Khan and Isani, 1994; Isani and Baloch, 1996; Wajid *et al.*, 2014; GOP, 2017-18). In the Balochistan province of Pakistan over 40% of the economy relies on sheep and wool

(<https://www.pakistantoday.com.pk/2013/03/01/modern-baloch-sheep-farmers-multiply-incomes-by-80-percent/>), so sheep have an important place in the socioeconomic life of the people of Balochistan. The principal sheep breeds present in the Balochistan province are Balochi, Beverigh, Harnai and Rakhshani. The population of the indigenous Balochi breed was measured at 3.73 million, which is higher than for other

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indigenous breeds in the province: Beverigh (1.65 million), Harnai (0.55 million), Rakhshani (0.04 million) (GOP, 2006). Sheep and goat farming is demonstrated to be a profitable business in rural areas of Balochistan, making a significant contribution to household income (Kakar *et al.*, 2013). Balochi sheep are characteristically fat-tailed, they generally have a white medium-sized body with a black, brown or spotted muzzle and legs, and they are well-adapted to the largest areas of harsh environmental conditions in Balochistan (Jahan *et al.*, 2012; Huma and Iqbal, 2019).

Variations in growth performance exist among sheep breeds and in different production systems (Ozder *et al.*, 2009). The system of production is characterized by seasonal and cyclic migration developed in Balochistan, which mainly depends on grazing. Different seasons have different kinds of pasture, but the nutrient requirement of sheep cannot be met during the winter season (Tariq *et al.*, 2011). The production system that provides optimal performance results is semi-intense, but the production cost is high (Bela and Aynalem, 2009). The hereditary likelihood for a specific class of sheep depends on availability of food and environmental conditions that largely affect the reproduction and production profitability of the animal (Kochapakdee *et al.*, 1994). Different body measurements play a key role for the assessment of production performance (Eyduran *et al.*, 2009; Iqbal *et al.*, 2019), where body height, length and girth have a significant influence as a combined outcome of hereditary and environmental factors (Rafeeq *et al.*, 2010). It is unfortunate that farmers are eager to keep large numbers of animals irrespective of their productivity, not identifying genetic potential or opting for proper breeding plans. Little importance has so far been given to study the hereditary and point of assessment of sheep production in Balochistan. Therefore, the aim of the present study was to establish baseline characteristics regarding the habitat, status, norms (morphological traits) and performance traits of the Balochi sheep breed in Balochistan.

METHODOLOGY

Baseline Study

The study was conducted over nine months (March 2018 to November 2018) on Balochi sheep (n=7049) from three districts (Kalat, Mastung, Quetta) of the Balochistan province and fifteen villages were visited for baseline study (Table 1). Comprehensive information relating to habitat, status, norms, morphological characteristics, feeding, breeding, production and management system, production performance, health practices, utility patterns and constrains of Balochi sheep reared in the region were collected on questionnaires specifically designed for this study. Priority was given to Balochi sheep rearing areas of the selected districts in order to observe the influence of crossbreeding and to know the existence of indigenous breeds in each locality. Households were randomly selected and secondary data on population statistics were obtained from district livestock offices. Some of the variables included in the study are summarized below.

Qualitative (morphological) characteristics: Sex, coat color pattern, coat type, horn shape and orientation, head profile and ear form of the animals were recorded. In addition to that, nutrients consumed (fodder and feed) and breeding procedure were recorded. Disease preventive measures and utility of the breed were also documented.

Quantitative (physiological) characteristics: Body weight and biometry measurements (body length, heart girth, wither height and tail length) of animals were taken randomly, and information about wool and milk production was recorded.

The data of male and female sheep from field farms in the respective areas (Kalat, Mastung, Quetta) and from the Multi-Purpose Sheep Research Station Yetabad, Loralai (MSRSYL) were recorded. The animals were weighed using a sheep weighing balance (± 500 gms). The biometry measurements were taken through the sheep measuring scale (± 1 cm). Pedigree records and performance data maintained at MSRSYL under semi-intensive conditions during 2015-2018 were recorded from birth to maturity. The study used the data of adult

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animals (ewes and rams). The collected data were summarized using MS-excel and analyzed using the t-test in SPSS-16 for Windows.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data were collected for Balochi sheep (n=7049) from 45 villages of three districts (Kalat, Mastung, Quetta) in the Balochistan province (Table 1). These districts are well known as Balochi sheep habitats. In the Kalat and Mastung districts the number of sheep in a flock ranged from five to 150 with an average of 30 animals. The Kalat district is the main hub of the Balochi breed, and because of its performance, adaptability, physique and white fleece coat, farmers have a preference in raising this breed. Balochi sheep are kept by Baloch clans that are generally not financially sound and are unaware about modern farming practices. The average number of persons in the studied farmer families was seven. A large majority of the farmers kept the sheep in open areas, whilst some farmers kept their animals in a shed overnight. Sheep were kept for the most part by grazing with infrequent supplementation. Normally other domesticated animals such as cows and goats were also kept on the same farms separated by some type of boundary. Rangelands were over grazed for most part from information obtained in the present study, but some grasses were cut and sustained or put away for winter-feeding. Because of a fodder shortage in winter, dry grain, corn, grasses, treated wheat straw and some supplements for sustainability were given to the sheep in winter. Two factors have caused rangeland degradation: excessive population growth and external social and economic forces (Tariq *et al.*, 2011). Farmers wanted to breed Balochi ewes with the best reputed rams of higher genetic potential of the same breed. The farmers of the Balochi regions do not allow this breed to cross with others on the grounds that they are less profitable than Balochi sheep. The economic conditions of many livestock farmers are not satisfactory, often with an unexploited quality in the genetic pool of their animals, which reduces profitability of the herds (Khan *et al.*, 2007; Tariq *et al.*, 2013).

Physical appearance

The recorded Balochi sheep were black and white with black marks on the legs and head, and their face color was generally black. They were generally polled animals. They had a firm body with medium height, pendulous belly and a fat tail. They had a medium-sized face with a Roman nose and their ears were generally medium-sized. The fleece was white and coarse.

Reproductive performance

The breeding of Balochi sheep was by natural mating, generally with one breeding male retained per flock. However in some larger size flocks, more than one male was kept for breeding purposes (one ram for 25 ewes). Other males were generally sold at 9-12 months for meat purposes. The average age of sexual maturity was 12-16 months for both males and females. The average age at first lambing was 19 to 25 months and the lambing interval was one year. Each ewe delivered an average of 6-9 lambs in her lifetime. The farmers mostly bred the animals in October to November and lambing took place in February to March. During these months the highest numbers of births were recorded. In the present study, twinning ratio values were estimated as 3.20%, whilst Tariq *et al.* (2011) estimated twinning ratios for the experimental station and field farms of Mengali sheep as 5.25% and 3.55%, respectively. In the current study the twin ratio for MSRSYL was found to be 6%.

Health management

A large proportion of the farmers did not inoculate their sheep against infections, generally due to lack of awareness. Parasitic infestation, enterotoxaemia and pneumonia accounted for real infections in the zone. Sheep mortality had a normal rate of 5% (extended 8-12%). Pneumonia was accounted as the primary cause behind

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sheep mortality in the winter season and enterotoxaemia in different seasons. Premature births accounted for 1-5% of mortality cases in November and December.

Utility

The Balochi sheep were kept for lamb, milk and fleece production. These sheep provided an alternative source of income, or farming them was done as a job or as a business. The sheep were prevalently butchered amid celebrations and religious events particularly Eid-ul-Azha. Livestock farmers utilized fleece to make hand-netted covers and carpets as well as being sold in marketplaces at high-quality prices. The customary framework Balochistan Landi (dried meat) was set up for utilization of meat during the winter season. Similarly, one of the methods that the farmers used for safeguarding meat production is through other food items like curd and lassi for their own utilization and spread foods such as ghee and kurt (dry cheddar) were sold in the neighborhood. Similar findings were reported by Tariq *et al.* (2011).

Biometric performance

The biometric results showed how location had a significant effect ($P < 0.05$) on body weight, body length, heart girth and wither height, but no effect on tail length (Table 2). Sex had a significant effect ($p < 0.05$) on growth performance. Males had greater height, girth and length compared to females ($P < 0.05$), whilst no significant difference was found in tail length (Table 3).

In an earlier study, the results for five sheep breeds in different parts of Balochistan showed significant ($P < 0.05$) differences for withers height, body length and heart girth (Rafeeq *et al.*, 2010). The Pearson correlation coefficients among all biometrical characteristics obtained for Balochi sheep are given in Table 4, showing very strong correlations between the biometrical traits ($P < 0.01$) and their respective correlation coefficients are statistically significant. It was demonstrated that keeping sheep under the semi-intensive conditions adapted by the farmers was slightly higher in cost. Gender also played an important role in the shape and weight of the sheep (Table 3). These conclusions were in agreement with those revealed by some different researchers (Rafeeq *et al.*, 2010; Tariq *et al.*, 2011, Bhatt *et al.*, 2018 and Iqbal *et al.*, 2019).

The biometric results of this study affirmed the findings of Tariq *et al.* (2011) who studied the information on biometry, profitable performance and survival of Mengali sheep. They established that male sheep were heavier in weight and had higher biometry parameters (body length, height, chest circumference) when compared with female sheep. Rafeeq *et al.* (2010), who assessed the profitable performance of five sheep breeds in Balochistan, observed that different sheep were significantly different ($P < 0.05$), for withers, height, body length and chest girth. A consistent growth performance was found in Balochi sheep compared with other breeds. It was agreed that the hereditary proficiency of breeds and ecological variables may enhance diversity in productive and biometric performance. Researchers also reported that chest girth is the best predictive equation for body weight in captured Stone's sheep (Singh *et al.*, 2014) and similar results were reported by Abdelhady *et al.* (2018).

CONCLUSION

The results of this study revealed that the Balochi breed is a distinctive sheep having unique characteristics and qualities. Animals kept under the semi-intensive conditions adapted by the farmers demonstrated to be slightly higher in cost. It was also observed that Balochi sheep farming is preferred because of its adaptability, great survival rate and growth performance.

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Tables

Table 1. Locations of Balochi sheep measured in three districts of Balochistan.

District	No. of villages	Male	Female	Total observations
Kalat	15	1065	1907	2972
Mastung	15	770	2040	2810
Quetta	15	429	838	1267
Grand total	45	2264	4785	7049

Table 2. Live body weights and biometric parameters of Balochi sheep (male n=170 and female n=210) from three districts and MSRSYL of Balochistan.

Location	Weight (kg)	Body length (cm)	Heart girth (cm)	Wither height (cm)	Tail length (cm)
Kalat	37.16 ± 0.48	82.01 ± 0.40	81.45 ± 0.40	72.02 ± 0.38	28.59 ± 0.30
Mastung	35.54 ± 0.39	80.75 ± 0.39	79.98 ± 0.43	71.43 ± 0.45	28.29 ± 0.31
Quetta	33.94 ± 0.23	78.69 ± 0.29	77.38 ± 0.43	69.43 ± 0.50	28.49 ± 0.25
MSRSYL	39.08 ± 0.52	85.10 ± 0.37	83.21 ± 0.48	74.56 ± 0.49	28.18 ± 0.31

Table 3. The effect of sex on biometric measurements of Balochi sheep (male n=680 and female n=840).

Variable	Sex	Mean (± se)	p-value
Weight (kg)	Male	36.43 ± 0.22	0.00
	Female	34.28 ± 0.19	
Body length (cm)	Male	81.63 ± 0.20	0.00
	Female	77.04 ± 0.23	
Heart girth (cm)	Male	80.50 ± 0.23	0.00
	Female	76.84 ± 0.20	
Wither height (cm)	Male	71.86 ± 0.24	0.00
	Female	70.53 ± 0.21	
Tail length (cm)	Male	28.38 ± 0.15	0.7
	Female	28.31 ± 0.13	

Table 4. Bivariate correlation of biometric characteristics of Balochi sheep.

	Body length	Heart girth	Wither height	Tail length
Body length	.227**	.175**	.068**	-.016
Heart girth		.358**	.174**	.054*
Wither height			.160**	-.015
Tail length				.024

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level